

Research Article

Design and Evaluation of Propranolol Loaded Bio Flexi Ocusert Using Cocos Nucifera Biopolymer

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Ocular inserts are sterile preparations, with a thin, multilayered, drug-impregnated, solid or semisolid consistency devices placed into cul-de-sac or conjunctiva sac. Ocular drug delivery is one of the most fascinating and challenging tasks facing the Pharmaceutical researchers. One of the major barriers of ocular medication is to obtain and maintain a therapeutic level at the site of action for prolonged period of time. Solvent casting technique was used to prepare the ocuserts. Ten formulation were prepared by using propranolol drug, cocos nucifera as biopolymer. The ocuserts were physically examined for colour and various other physical parameters were evaluated. Based on the physical parameters further studies were carried out like stability, invitro release studies. The therapeutic efficacy of an ocular drug can be greatly improved by prolonging its contact with the corneal surface. Newer ocular drug delivery systems are being explored to develop extended duration and controlled release strategy.

Keywords: Propranolol, Bio Flexi Ocusert, Cocos Nucifera Biopolymer.

INTRODUCTION

The eye as a portal for drug delivery is generally used for local therapy against systemic therapy in order to avoid the risk of eye damage from high blood concentrations of the drug, which is not intended. The unique anatomy, physiology and biochemistry of the eye render this organ impervious to foreign substances, thus presenting a constant challenge to the formulator to circumvent the protective barriers of the eye without causing permanent tissue damage. Most ocular treatments like eye drops and suspensions call for the topical administration of ophthalmically active drugs to the tissues around the ocular cavity. These dosage forms are easy to instill but suffer from the inherent drawback that the majority of the medication they contain is immediately diluted in the tear film as soon as the eye drop solution is instilled into the cul-de-sac and is rapidly drained away from the precorneal cavity by constant tear flow and lacrimo-nasal drainage. Therefore, only a very small fraction of the instilled dose is absorbed by the target tissue for this reason, concentrated solutions and

frequent dosing are required for the instillation to achieve an adequate level of therapeutic effect. One of the new classes of drug delivery systems, ocular inserts, which are gaining worldwide praise, release drugs at a pre-programmed rate for a longer period by increasing the precorneal residence time. Propranolol is a sympatholytic non-selective beta blocker. Sympatholytic are used to treat hypertension, anxiety and panic and glaucoma. It was the first successful beta blocker developed. Propranolol is rapidly and completely absorbed, with peak plasma levels achieved approximately 1–3 hours after ingestion. The main metabolite 4-hydroxypropranolol, with a longer half-life (5.2–7.5 hours) than the parent compound (3–4 hours), is also pharmacologically active. Propranolol is a highly lipophilic drug achieving high concentrations in the brain. Propranolol is a non-selective beta blocker, that is, it blocks the action of epinephrine and norepinephrine on both β_1 - and β_2 -adrenergic receptors. It has little intrinsic sympathomimetic activity (ISA) but has strong membrane stabilizing activity. Coconut is highly nutritious and rich in fiber, vitamins, and

minerals. It is classified as a "functional food" because it provides many health benefits beyond its nutritional content. It is also a very good source of B-complex vitamins such as folates, riboflavin, niacin, thiamin, and pyridoxine. These vitamins are essential in the sense that body requires them from external sources to replenish. Coconut meat and water contain a very good amount of potassium. 100 g of fresh meat contains 356 mg% or 7.5% of daily required levels of potassium.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Material- coconut bio-polymer were collected.

I. Preparation of Ocuserts

The various formulations of bio flexi ocusert were prepared by solvent casting method. Different bio-flexi ocusert (1:1 to 1:10) were prepared with varying concentration of the biopolymer. Biopolymer was taken in mortar pestle and triturated properly for the fine powder. After that 50 mg of dextrose & 50mg of glucose was added along with 100 mg of nanosized drug (propranolol). Then 10 ml of distill water was added and triturated properly in uniform direction. After that magnetic stirring was done for 45 minutes and sonication was performed (3cycle). After that the mixture was uniformly spreaded on a petri-dish and dried at room temperature. Bio-flexi film was obtained.

Formulation detail

formulation	FB1 (1:1)	FB2 (1:2)	FB3 (1:3)	FB4 (1:4)	FB5 (1:5)	FB6 (1:6)	FB7 (1:7)	FB8 (1:8)	FB9 (1:9)	FB9 (1:10)
Propranolol(mg)	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
Cocos nucifera biopolymer	1%	2%	3%	4%	5%	6%	7%	8%	9%	10%
dextrose	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50
glucose	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50
Distilled water	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10

Flowchart-

EVALUATION PARAMETER-

The ocuserts were evaluated for thickness, folding endurance, drug content uniformity, surface pH, and in-vitro diffusion studies

Thickness- Insert thickness was measured by a Vernier caliper at five different points on the film. The mean thickness and standard deviation (SD) were calculated.

Sr. No	Formulation	Thickness
1	FC1	0.23
2	FC2	0.28
3	FC3	0.32
4	FC4	0.62
5	FC5	0.42
6	FC6	0.48
7	FC7	0.52
8	FC8	0.58
9	FC9	0.48
10	FC10	0.42

Weight uniformity - Weight uniformity of bio-flexi ocusert determined by taking weight of ten bio- flexi ocusert of sizes 1 square cm diameter from every

batch and weight individually on electronic balance. The avg. weight was calculated.

S. No	Formulation	Weight Uniformity
1	FC1	15.8
2	FC2	18.6
3	FC3	27.9
4	FC4	25.7
5	FC5	25.7
6	FC6	17.6
7	FC7	21.5
8	FC8	26.7
9	FC9	18.6
10	FC10	15.7

Folding Endurance- Folding Endurance of the film was determined by repeatedly folding the inserts at the same place till it breaks. The ocuserts was folded in

the center, between finger and thumb and then opened. This was one folding. The number of times, the film could be folded at the same place without breaking gave the value of folding endurance

S.No	Formulation	Folding Indurance
1	FC1	118
2	FC2	121
3	FC3	116
4	FC4	134
5	FC5	164
6	FC6	158
7	FC7	172
8	FC8	132
9	FC9	142
10	FC10	168

Drug content uniformity- Uniformity of drug content was determined by assaying the individual inserts. Three inserts from each batch were powdered individually and each was dissolved in 100 ml of

purified water by stirring on a magnetic stirrer for 2 hours. The absorbance of each of these solutions was then measured on UV-visible spectrophotometer at 290 nm.

S. No	Formulation	%Drug Content Uniformity
1	Fc1	85.82
2	Fc2	66.41
3	Fc3	95.52
4	Fc4	68.65
5	Fc5	92.53
6	Fc6	64.92
7	Fc7	83.58
8	Fc8	93.28
9	Fc9	64.92
10	Fc10	85.82

In-vitro diffusion studies the in-vitro drug release studies were carried out using diffusion cell. 0.7 ml of isotonic phosphate buffer of pH 7.4 was placed in the donor chamber, which acted as tear fluid. Ocusert was placed in the donor compartment over a egg shell

membrane. 25 ml of isotonic phosphate buffer was taken as the receptor medium and the apparatus was maintained at $37 \pm 2^\circ \text{C}$ and was continuously stirred using magnetic stirrer. The samples were withdrawn at regular intervals and analyzed at 290 nm.

Figure- Invitro drug release of propranolol ocuser

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The prepared ocusert were evaluated for the thickness of each film using a micrometer. The average of five readings was taken. The mean thickness, standard deviation and percent coefficient of variation were calculated. All the eight formulations, measured thickness with low standard deviation values ensured the uniformity of the films prepared by solvent casting technique. The estimation of drug content uniformity was found to be almost same with their low standard deviation value. Cumulative percentage drug release of each ocusert in the *in vitro* release studies was based on the mean content of the drug present in the respective films. The weight of all the ocusert was found to be uniform indicating good distribution of drug, polymer. Thickness specifications may be set on an individual product basis. There were no marked variations in the thickness of ocuserts within each formulation indicating uniform behavior of ocusert throughout the sealing process. The thickness of the ocuserts of all formulation were tabled. Drug release was carried out by M.S Diffusion apparatus. The mechanism of propranolol released from the bioflexi ocusert was studied by fitting the dissolution data in different kinetic models such as Zero order, First order, Higuchi Matrix, Peppas Korsmeyer and Hixon Crowell and determining the R² values of the release profile corresponding to each model. Its % drug release, t_{50%} and t_{80%} were calculated on the basis of M.S diffusion apparatus. For formulations by *cocos nucifera* the drug release pattern for **FCN1-FCN10 based on t₈₀** was found to be **FCN9 (1:9) > FCN5 (1:5) > FCN7 (1:7) > FCN6 (1:6) > FCN10 (1:10) > FCN2 (1:2) > FCN4 (1:4) > FCN9 (1:9) > FCN1 (1:1) > FCN3 (1:3)**. In-vitro drug release was performed for all the formulations and the data indicate that drug loaded formulations show the sustained release behavior. Graph was plotted

between % Cpr and time, the R² value, T50% and T80% was calculated from graph, the **FCN9 (1:9)** formulation was found to be the best formulation showing an R² value of **0.9896**, **t50% of 5 hrs and t80% of 23 hrs** respectively. According to the release kinetics the best fit model was found to be **Hixon Crowell** with **SUPERCASE 11 TRANSPORT** as the mechanism of drug release. From each batch randomly five ocuserts were selected and weighed. It ranges from 15.7 to 27.9. The weight uniformity of ocuserts of all formulations were tabled. Use of less amount of plasticizer was observed to cause brittleness in the medicated discs, but use of greater amount of plasticizer (1ml plasticizer per 10 ml) displayed little opaqueness and good folding endurance.

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